

The Influence of Leadership, Motivation and Work Environment on Employee Performance (Case Study at Citeureup Health Center)

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze the influence of Leadership, Motivation, Work Environment on the Performance of Citeureup Health Center Employees. either partially or simultaneously. This research is descriptive quantitative, that is explaining the relationship between variables by analyzing numerical data (numbers) using statistical methods through hypothesis testing. The research method used is the survey method, which is a study to study the dynamics of the correlation between risk factors and the influence of observations or data collection approaches. The sample used by researchers is saturated or census sample. as many as 100 employees at the Citeureup Health Center. Based on the results of the research and discussion, it can be concluded that leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Citeureup Health Center employees. Which means that to improve performance, the leader must lead in a wise way according to the employee's situation, motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Citeureup Health Center employees. This means that work results will be better if employees have the motivation to carry out their duties and develop their abilities, the work environment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of Citeureup Health Center employees. This means that work results are better if employees have a work environment such as adequate infrastructure and facilities in carrying out their work.

Keywords:- Leadership, Motivation, Work Environment and Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Organizations are one thing that expects not only competent and professional human resources, but especially how hard and ready they are to achieve appropriate results and will affect the performance and motivation of the employees themselves. This is the same as HR which is a key factor in the organization [1]. Good resources will provide good success for all human beings. This is because human resources are an important element in an organization. Personnel, both in management positions and as employees, are an important factor in organizations. An agency or company cannot function if it does not have staff who can carry out their duties properly. If the human resources are of high quality, the

output will be of high quality. The performance of an employee directly affects the advancement or withdrawal of an agency or company. The decrease in employee performance causes the employee's performance to be not optimal.

An agency engaged in the service sector must carry out its duties properly. This is because service becomes an important role of success in the organization. With a good level of service provided will produce a good ability to provide work motivation for all human beings. From the data, it shows that there was a significant increase in the Citeureup Health Center where the services provided for the Bogor Regency area occurred. This can be seen where in 2018 there were 750 patients, in 2019 there were 1200 patients, in 2020 there were 1450 patients and in 2021 there were 1700 patients.

The Citeureup Health Center is a health center operating in the West Java region, namely in Citeureup, Bogor Regency, which is a health technical service unit that seeks to drive health-oriented development in order to maximize health services to the community. The Citeureup Health Center in Bogor district always prioritizes the maintenance and improvement of services that provide promotive and curative efforts to create a healthy and prosperous society. The Head of the Citeureup Health Center in Bogor Regency is the person in charge of health services at the sub-district level, as well as a leader who provides maximum service to people in need. But in reality the head of government who has absolute power is implemented by the Head of the Citeureup Health Center with the aim of motivating increased employee performance even though the role of the Head the Citeureup Health Center is very important in providing a conducive work environment to support performance so that it can be achieved optimally. Based on information obtained from the at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency, it can be seen that the results of employee performance are as follows:

No	Point of employee performance	2018 Performance		2019 Performance		2020 Performance	
		Amount	%	Amount	%	Amount	%
1	Very good	40	40	20	10	10	10
2	Good	40	40	10	30	10	10
3	Standard	10	10	10	30	50	50
4	Substandard	10	10	60	60	30	30
	Amount	100	100	100	100	100	100

Table 1: Data on the Assessment of Increase and Decrease in Employee Performance

From the data table above, there are performance points for assessing data on increases and decreases in employee performance as follows:

- There is an increase in standard performance points in 2020 of 50.00%
- There was a very significant increase in substandard performance points in 2019 of 60.00%

Overall, the data for performance increases and decreases in 2018, 2019, 2020 for performance point 1 "Very Good" has increased by 40.00%, in 2019 it has decreased to 20.00% and again decreased in 2020 by 10.00%. At performance point 2 "Good" there was an increase in 2018 by 40.00%, and there was a decrease in 2019 by 10.00% to 2020 again decreasing by 20.00%. The performance of the 3 "Standards" in 2018 was 10.00% and in 2019 it remained at 10.00%, then in 2020 there was an increase of 60.00%. In performance 4 "Below Standard" in 2018 it was 10.00% from 2019 it increased by 60.00%, but in 2020 there was a decrease of 30.00%.

From the data obtained, employees who have very good, good categories experience a decrease every year and standards experience an increase in performance, but it is unfortunate that employees who are in the substandard category also experience an increase. In order to improve the provision of comprehensive and sustainable health center services, human resources are needed, which have professionalism, their tasks are more efficient and effective. Someone is needed who can become a leader in the business to produce professional health workers who have the aim of updating the latest knowledge in the field of health professions.

There are several variables related to performance, including:

- Leadership
- Motivation
- Organizational culture
- Work environment
- Job satisfaction

To get results that are in accordance with the conditions of the institution, the authors conducted interviews with employees at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency. To get the results of the analysis that are in accordance with the conditions of the institution, the authors conducted interviews with employees at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency. This decline in performance is influenced by factors such as work motivation, work environment and others.

II. LITERATURE

A. Leadership

Leadership can be interpreted as an activity that is able to attract the attention of employees or subordinates to follow the rules in the organization. The leader invites employees or subordinates to carry out tasks that have been carefully planned by the organization or group [2]. A leader is someone who uses his authority and leadership, directing subordinates in doing part of their work to achieve goals. Leader is a leader who has leadership traits and authority (personality authority). Leadership is a way for a leader to influence the behavior of subordinates, in order to work together and work productively to achieve organizational goals [3].

B. Motivation

Because of the quality of thought processes, fundamental needs, desires, and motivating force values, motivation may be a potential energy save that a person needs to be utilized and discharged [4]. This depends on the quality of support and opportunities that exist where the energy will be utilized by workers. Inspiration is frequently interpreted as a role model who motivates someone to act in a certain way, hence inspiration is a driving force behind someone's conduct [5].

C. Work Environment

Everything that is around employees and that may influence how well they perform the tasks assigned, such as cleanliness, music, lighting, and other factors, is referred to as the "work environment" in this definition. According to the aforementioned comprehension, the employee's response to a certain work environment, constitutes the scope of the work environment. Employees will be impacted by the leadership style democratic leaders choose. One aspect that affects employee behavior is the work environment that develops within the organization. The physical aspects of the workplace, such as the buildings, rooms, cleanliness, orderliness, and other infrastructure and facilities, can be understood as the workplace environment. Moreover, it can be viewed psychologically as a cozy, enjoyable, overcrowded, or monotonous work environment [6].

D. Employee Performance

Performance is the outcome of work that a person completes in accordance with the demands of the position. Work standards are requirements that must be met as part of a job in order to achieve objectives [7]. The outcome of an employee's quality and amount of work produced while doing their duties in line with their given obligations is known as employee performance (also known as work performance) [8].

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on previous research, the framework developed in the research is as follows.

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework

Based on the picture above, there are seven hypotheses in this study, namely:

H1: Leadership has a significant effect on employee performance.

H2: Motivation has a significant effect on employee performance.

H3: Work environment Has a significant effect on employee performance.

IV. RESEARCH AND METHODS

The authors used a quantitative statistical analysis method, namely on a survey scale to express the weight ratio between variables and other variables. The author distributed a questionnaire to all 100 employees at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency. Analyzing the data, the authors used the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with SmartPLS 3.0 to validate structural measurements and models.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The respondents characteristic data was obtained from a questionnaire that had been distributed to all employees in the Citeureup Health Center, totaling 100 people and most of the respondent profiles used by researchers were female. The dominance of female employee respondents is due to agencies engaged in the health service sector, with the nature of the work being challenging and with lots of risks so that more female employees are needed.

Based on their education, most of the respondents had diploma three education, namely as many as 45%, 25% had an undergraduate degree and 30% had high school education. With the majority of employees having diploma three, this is due to jobs that require technical skills such as nursing, midwifery, pharmacy, public health so that graduates of diploma three majoring in nursing, midwifery, pharmacy, public health are considered more ready to work.

The following are the results of the data analysis that has been carried out.

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	CR	CA	AVE				
Leadership	X1.2	0.822	0.908	0.886	0,510				
	X1.3	0.796							
	X1.4	0.782							
	X1.5	0.890							
	X1.6	0.834							
	X1.7	0.904							
	X1.9	0.901							
	X1.10	0.744							
	X1.11	0.866							
	X1.12	0.874							
	Motivation	X2.1				0.772	0.958	0.950	0.695
		X2.2				0.834			
X2.3		0.771							
X2.4		0.891							
X2.5		0.875							
X2.6		0.920							
X2.7		0.746							
X2.9		0.921							
X2.10		0.982							
X2.11		0.983							
Work Environment		X2.1	0.875	0.962	0.956	0.740			
		X2.2	0.953						
	X2.3	0.861							
	X2.4	0.874							
	X3.7	0.896							
	X3.8	0.900							
	X3.9	0.933							
	X3.10	0.890							
	X3.11	0.874							
	Employee Performance	Y.1	0.896				0.940	0.929	0.568
		Y.2	0.896						
		Y.3	0.866						
Y.4		0.784							
Y.5		0.889							
Y.6		0.904							
Y.7		0.770							
Y.8		0.937							
Y.9		0.858							
Y.10		0.766							
Y.11		0.880							
Y.12		0.876							

Table 2: Construct Reliability and Validity Results

The indicator has good validity and reliability if the outer loading value, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach Alpha value are greater than 0.70 [9]. In addition, it is also accompanied by an AVE value greater than 0.5. As shown

in Table 2, all the outer loading, Composite Reliability, and Cronbach Alpha values of this study exceeded 0.7 and the AVE values exceeded 0.5. Based on these results, it can be said that all variables are valid and reliable.

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Employee Performance	0.771	0.764

Table 3: R Square

In the table above, it can be seen that the value of R Square for the performance variable obtained is 0.771 or 77.1% indicating the model is in the strong category because the R square is in the > range of 0.67. These results show that leadership, motivation and work

environment together have an influence of 77.1% on performance, while the remaining 22.9% is a large contribution of influence given by other factors that were not studied.

Hypothesis	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values	Information
Leadership -> Employee Performance	0.273	4.286	0.000	Significant
Motivation -> Employee Performance	0.461	4.931	0.000	Significant
Work Environment-> Employee Performance	0.317	2.628	0.009	Significant

Table 4: Results of Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1 explains the effect of leadership on employee performance. By looking at the results of existing data processing, it is known that the path coefficient value is 0.273 with a t-statistics value = 4,286 > 1.96 and p-values 0.000 < 0.05 so that H1 is accepted, this means that the leadership variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it states that leadership variables have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Citeureup Health Center, because to improve performance, the leader must lead in a wise way according to the employee's situation and be able to accept the proposals given by subordinates in order to receive the input given so that they can make the right decisions, therefore, leadership affects the performance of employees at the Citeureup Health Center. The above is in line with the results of research which proves that there is an influence of leadership variables on performance variables [10][11].

Every organization is made up of people, and it's a leader's job to work together and leverage the help of those people to achieve the goals of the organization. Performance is a function of ability, leadership and opportunity to perform. Thus leadership is one of the factors that most influence the level of individual performance of employees, where employees learn a lot from how the leader behaves. Leaders are also expected to be a liaison between employees, can provide clear information and can make wise decisions.

Leadership is a factor that cannot be separated from the development or decline of a company. If the leader is favored, respected, has support, cooperation, has a good relationship with the group, the leader in question can reduce his dependence on formal authority. This situation will give great control and influence to the leadership. On the other hand, if the leader is not liked or distrusted, then the leader will not be able to lead formally and may have to rely on the authority for the completion of all tasks.

The leadership at the Citeureup Health Center in Bogor Regency received a fairly high response from respondents. This is because the leadership that has occurred so far is quite friendly to its employees, by paying attention to the work of employees so as to encourage employees to be able to complete their work with full responsibility and the quality of service is well maintained. The leader can be a driving force and role model for subordinates for the agencies he leads. The leadership is also willing to accept the proposals given by subordinates and is willing to include these proposals in the operation of activities. The proposal received by the superior will make employees feel happy and feel

responsible for the achievement of the existing activity program at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency.

However, with a number of activities, leaders are not always able to monitor the work of their employees. Leaders are also less active in encouraging employees to be able to realize service renewal efforts in the organization. With these limitations or weaknesses, presumably the leader can give full confidence to his subordinates in completing the tasks that are his responsibility so that employees are motivated to be able to work responsibly even though it is not always under the supervision of the leader.

Hypothesis 2 explains the effect of motivation on employee performance. By looking at the results of existing data processing, it is known that the path coefficient value is 0.461 with t-statistics values = 4,931 > 1.96 and p-values 0.000 < 0.05 so that H2 is accepted, this means that the motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it states that the motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Citeureup Health Center, because this is that work results will be better if employees have the motivation to perform their duties and develop their abilities, it is necessary to be given a reward boost in the form of bonuses and benefits that can increase employee motivation. therefore, motivation has a significant effect on the performance of employees at the Citeureup Health Center. The above is in line with the results of research which proves that there is an influence of motivation variables on performance variables [12][13].

Employees at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency, have high motivation to get the best position in the office, and strive to achieve this position with their abilities. Employees always have creativity for the advancement of their achievements by trying to achieve work standards in completing each task. Employees who have high motivation will want to succeed in pursuing a career so that it motivates them to work hard. On the other hand, employees who have low motivation can experience failure in achieving the desired goals. On the other hand, employees who have high achievements will be respected by other employees. Employees with high work motivation will be able to complete their tasks according to the specified target time.

Hypothesis 3 explains the effect of the work environment on employee performance. By looking at the results of existing data processing, it is known that the path coefficient value is 0.317 with t-statistics values = 2,628 > 1.96 and p-values 0.009 < 0.05 so that H3 is

accepted, this means that the work environment variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency.

Based on the results of hypothesis testing in table, it states that the variables of the work environment have a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Citeureup Health Center, because to improve the performance of work results, it is better if employees have a work environment such as adequate infrastructure and facilities in carrying out work where a comfortable work environment can improve employee performance in their daily work. therefore, the work environment has a significant effect on the performance of employees at the Citeureup Health Center. The above is in line with the results which proves that the work environment affects employee performance [14][15].

The work environment for employees will have no small influence on the operation of the agency. The work environment will affect employees so that directly or indirectly it will affect the productivity of the agency. A good work environment that satisfies employees will certainly improve the performance of employees. On the other hand, an unfavorable work environment will reduce the performance of employees and indirectly also reduce the productivity of the agency.

The work environment has a considerable contribution in improving performance. Environmental conditions in variations – relatively simple variations in temperature, noise, lighting, or regional quality can drive meaningful effects on employee attitudes and performance. In addition, a design that takes into account the number of workspaces, their arrangement or layout and the level of personal power exerted, affects the performance and level of employee satisfaction. No less important is the non-physical environment in the form of relationships that occur between employees and superiors or with fellow employees. The occurrence of harmony or harmony among employees and with superiors will support the completion of tasks that are the responsibility of employees.

The work environment at the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency, is considered good by its employees. This is shown from the non-physical environment in the form of leaders who have a harmonious and good working relationship with all employees without discriminating against the status of pegawai, the occurrence of a good relationship between fellow colleagues is open to each other in communicating if there are problems or conflicts in the company's work environment. Good lighting in the workplace can help employees in getting work done. Security in the workplace has been able to make employees work comfortably so that employees can work with peace of mind. However, it is also necessary to pay attention to the arrangement of work equipment and the arrangement of documents / archives in the office so that they can be

arranged more neatly so as to make it easier for employees when serving people who need health services.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded as follows:

- Leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Citeureup Health Center. The leader can lead in a wise way according to the situation of the employee and is able to accept the proposals given by subordinates so that they can make the right decisions for the progress of the institution he leads.
- Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Citeureup Health Center. Employees who have high work motivation will try to improve their work performance by being affiliated with fellow colleagues so that their performance is even higher.
- The work environment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees of the Citeureup Health Center. A well-organized, safe, comfortable work environment with harmonious relationships with fellow employees has positively improved employee performance.

Based on the description of the conclusions previously stated, the study suggests the following:

- The leadership always gives encouragement to its employees to be able to realize renewal efforts in health services at the Puskesmas, so that employees can serve people who need health services deftly and friendly in achieving goals according to the vision and mission of the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency.
- Employees always increase their work motivation by trying not to fail in achieving the desired goals, therefore employees need to be given training in accordance with their position and competence. With this positive motivation, it is hoped that employees can contribute to improving the performance of the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency.
- Employees are always involved in maintaining and improving a good work environment such as existing facilities and infrastructure, so as to create a healthy and adequate work environment in order to improve the performance of the Citeureup Health Center, Bogor Regency.

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